

CHARACTERIZATION OF RANAVIRUSES INFECTING DIFFERENT CLASSES OF
ECTOTHERMIC VERTEBRATES

By

CODY REID KAISER CONRAD

A THESIS PRESENTED TO THE GRADUATE SCHOOL
OF THE UNIVERSITY OF FLORIDA IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT
OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF
MASTER OF SCIENCE

UNIVERSITY OF FLORIDA

2022

© 2022 Cody Reid Kaiser Conrad

To Ana-Maria Proctor, who believed in me so fiercely that I learned to believe in myself

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am fortunate to exist in such a time and space as this; with access to modern medicine, global cuisines, and a diverse community that provides ample services, Gainesville, Florida in the early 21st century is not perfect (in fact, many call it “the swamp”), but is still one of my few homes on Earth.

Greater than my physical setting is the emotional one that my family, friends, and coworkers have provided for me. I have had the distinct privilege of feeling like a prince many times throughout my life and for this sentiment I thank: Priam for his wisdom, beard, love, and trust to let me make decisions for myself: Hecuba for her interest in my future, constant support, love, and exceptional work ethic: Logan for being the Odysseus to my Menelaus: Luke for being the Hector to my Paris (and vice versa). I thank Cheyenne, Laura, Armani, and Giovanni for confirming that rainbows follow the rain, Joey for rising through adversity and lifting others above himself, J for his knowledge, inspiration, and never quitting, and Joe for demonstrating what a good student is supposed to be.

I certainly could not have been successful in this endeavor without the guidance and expertise of Drs. Chinchar, Longo, Ossiboff, and Subramaniam, who comprised my committee. I am beyond grateful for the opportunity that Drs. Waltzek and Subramaniam have given me. I appreciate all of the help that I have received at the lab and beyond: from Dr. Viadanna, Dr. Megarani, Dr. Yanong, Dr. Koda, Dr. Kane, Ross, Jordan Vann, Segrest Farms, Dr. Chinchar and the other dream team of '95-96 (sorry, Chicago), the employees of Blue Jay Point County Park and the NCDVLS, Roland Corporation, and many, many others.

I would be remiss if I also did not acknowledge the adversity that I have faced; for, it is only due to rejection that I discover a new passion.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	<u>page</u>
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	4
LIST OF TABLES	6
LIST OF FIGURES	5
ABSTRACT	9
CHAPTER	
1 THE GENUS <i>RANAVIRUS</i>	10
Host Range	10
Clinical Considerations for Ranaviruses	13
Diagnostic Assessment	14
Treatment	14
Prevention of Spread	15
2 GENOMIC SEQUENCING OF RANAVIRUS ISOLATES FROM THREE-SPINED STICKLEBACKS (<i>GASTEROSTEUS ACULEATUS</i>) AND RED-LEGGED FROGS (<i>RANA AURORA</i>)	16
Methods	16
Cell Culture and Virus Enrichment	16
Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis	17
Results	17
Cell Culture and Virus Enrichment	17
Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis	18
Discussion	18
3 PHYLOGENOMIC CHARACTERIZATION OF A RANAVIRUS FROM A MORTALITY EVENT IN NORTH CAROLINA	31
Methods	31
Case History	31
Histopathology	32
Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)	32
RNAscope® In Situ Hybridization (ISH)	33
Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis	34
Results	35
Histopathology	35
Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)	35
RNAscope® In Situ Hybridization (ISH)	35

Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis	36
Discussion.....	36
LIST OF REFERENCES	51
BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH	57

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>page</u>
2-1 Virus abbreviations, names, and GenBank accession numbers of the ranaviruses used in the phylogenetic analysis.....	20
2-2 Predicted open reading frames for the genomes of SBV and TV2.....	23
3-1 Virus abbreviations, names, and GenBank accession numbers of the ranaviruses used in the phylogenetic analysis.....	39
3-2 qPCR results from the tadpole and turtle samples.....	42
3-3 Predicted open reading frames for the genomes of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5.....	43

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>		<u>page</u>
2-1	Microscopic examination of cytopathic effect (CPE) characteristics of TV2 in the EPC cell line.	21
2-2	Maximum-likelihood phylogram depicting the relationship of SBV and TV2 to 44 other ranaviruses based on the concatenated genome-wide locally colinear block alignments.	30
3-1	Histology and RNAscope® in situ hybridization results from turtle and tadpole tissues targeted for ISH.	41
3-2	Comparison of the coding sequence of the predicted neurofilament H1 genes of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5.	42
3-3	Maximum-likelihood phylogram depicting the relationship of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 to 46 other ranaviruses based on the concatenated genome-wide locally colinear block alignments.	50

Abstract of Thesis Presented to the Graduate School
of the University of Florida in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of Master of Science

CHARACTERIZATION OF RANAVIRUSES INFECTING DIFFERENT CLASSES OF
ECTOTHERMIC VERTEBRATES

By

Cody Reid Kaiser Conrad

May 2022

Chair: Kuttichantran Subramaniam
Major: Veterinary Medical Sciences

Ranaviruses are emerging pathogens that cause mortality events throughout the world. The amount of research being performed on these viruses has been increasing substantially since the discovery of the type species, *Frog virus 3*, in 1965 by Granoff et al. 1965, because of the threat that they pose to wild and captive ectothermic vertebrates and the virologically important features they present. In this study, we report the complete genome sequences of two ranavirus isolates collected from fish and tadpoles in California 25 years ago and two strains collected from turtles and tadpoles in North Carolina almost two years ago. It is apparent that frog virus 3 (FV3) circulates in the wild and is present in sylvatic populations from the west coast of the United States to the east coast. Host animals from the preliminary study included the three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) and the northern red-legged frog (*Rana aurora*). Host animals from the second study comprised the eastern painted turtle (*Chrysemys picta picta*) and the common frog (*Rana temporaria*). Phylogenomic analyses revealed that the two pairs of strains are most closely related to each other when compared on a full-genome level to 44 other ranavirus isolates and suggest interclass transmission in the wild setting. Additional research is needed in order to understand ranavirus host and geographic range.

CHAPTER 1 THE GENUS *RANAVIRUS*

The two subfamilies of the family *Iridoviridae*, *Alphairidovirinae* and *Betairidovirinae*, include viruses that infect vertebrates and invertebrates, respectively. Members of the genus *Ranavirus* (subfamily *Alphairidovirinae*) are a group of viruses that cause disease in at least 175 species of reptiles, amphibians, and fish (Duffus et al. 2015). Some species of *Ranavirus* are capable of infecting multiple species at a given geographic location (Mao et al. 1999) and can even be transmitted among different taxonomic classes of cold-blooded vertebrates (Brenes et al. 2014). One of the most important species within the genus *Ranavirus*, *Frog virus 3* (FV3), was discovered serendipitously (Granoff et al. 1965), studied extensively as the representative of a novel virus family, but not appreciated for its pathogenic significance in animals until some 20 years later (Chinchar et al. 2009). The scientific community now recognizes that these viruses are important pathogens in wild and captive animal populations. Ranaviruses are double stranded DNA viruses (Goorha and Murti 1982) that possess numerous genes that facilitate virus replication and suppress host immune function, enabling them to be effectively infectious and lethal (Eaton et al. 2007). Remarkably, virions that have been rendered noninfectious (by UV or heat) retain the ability to disable cellular transcription and translation (Cordier et al. 1981). Furthermore, some ranaviruses, such as epizootic hematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNV), can survive in frozen tissues for over two years and can persist without any decrease in viral concentration in distilled water for 97 days at 15°C (Langdon 1989).

Host Range

Although numerous strains exist among several virus species within the genus *Ranavirus*, only a handful have been detected in aquaculture animals. Furthermore, only a few species of fish are known to be vulnerable to disease caused by ranaviruses. Largemouth bass (*Micropterus*

salmoides) are susceptible to Santee-Cooper Ranavirus (SCRV = Largemouth Bass Virus, LMBV) in wild populations (Grizzle and Brunner 2003) while striped bass (*Morone saxatilis*) encounter lower mortality in experimental settings than their fellow perciform, the largemouth bass (Zilberg et al. 2000). Cultured marbled sleeper goby (*Oxyeleotris marmorata*) have been reported in Thailand with FV3 (Prasankok et al. 2005). In the United States, pallid sturgeon (*Scaphirhynchus albus*) in a Missouri hatchery experienced a die-off from an outbreak of FV3 (Waltzek et al. 2014). Russian (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*), Lake (*Acipenser fulvescens*), and White (*Acipenser transmontanus*) sturgeon have been found to be highly susceptible to FV3 in experimental settings (Waltzek et al. 2014). Most other experimentally infected farm species are not susceptible to FV3, including black bullhead (*Ameiurus melas*), western mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*), and bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*) (Gobbo et al. 2010, Brenes et al. 2014). Singapore grouper iridovirus (SGIV) has been a serious cause of die-offs in brown-spotted grouper (*Epinephelus tauvina*) and yellow grouper (*Epinephelus awoara*) in Taiwan (Qin et al. 2003, Murali et al. 2002). SGIV has been responsible for multiple die-offs of maricultured groupers across Southeast Asia. Cod ranavirus (CoIV) was isolated from wild atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) and turbot (*Psetta maxima*) but not well characterized (Ariel et al. 2010). Research indicates that many species act as carriers but do not experience disease due to the virus. EHNIV has been responsible for die-offs in redbfin perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) in Australia (Langdon et al. 1986, Whittington et al. 2010). The black bullhead (*Ameiurus melas*) and northern pike (*Esox lucius*) are susceptible to EHNIV in experimental settings (Jensen et al. 2009).

Amphibians tend to not only experience more severe disease with ranavirus infections, but are also more widely affected, both geographically and taxonomically (Duffus et al. 2015).

Three ranavirus species are known to cause disease in amphibians, including *Frog virus 3*, *Ambystoma tigrinum virus* (ATV), and *Common midwife toad virus* (CMTV) (Duffus et al. 2015). FV3 has been responsible for numerous disease outbreaks in North and South America, Central America, Europe, and Asia, among host species such as *Lithobates catesbeianus*, *Craugastor fitzingeri*, *Rana temporaria*, and *Rana dybowskii*, respectively (Miller et al. 2007, Mazzoni et al. 2009, Whitfield et al. 2013, Cunningham et al. 1993, Xu et al. 2010). It is worth noting that amphibian infections caused by FV3 have been documented in both captive and wild settings. Ranacultured American bullfrogs (*Lithobates catesbeianus*) have suffered multiple mass mortality events throughout the world. In contrast, ATV has a much less extensive geographic and host range and is restricted in the wild to the western United States (Ridenhour & Storfer 2008). Some of the known hosts that are vulnerable to ATV are endangered and the virus is therefore important to amphibian conservation (Jancovich et al. 1997, Picco et al. 2007). CMTV, similar to ATV, is not yet a globally distributed species, with its presence only observed in Europe, China, and the United States; although, the instances of CMTV-like viruses in the latter two countries has been documented only a few times and once, respectively (Geng et al. 2011, Claytor et al. 2017). CMTV has been responsible for several significant mortality events in Spain (Price et al. 2014). The most noteworthy report of CMTV is the recombination that is known to occur between it and FV3 and the potential increase in virulence due to this genetic phenomenon (Claytor et al. 2017, Vilaça et al. 2019).

Ranavirus infections in reptiles are infrequent in comparison to fish and amphibians and few studies have been conducted to understand their impact on reptiles. However, FV3 infections have been detected within wild populations of turtles in some eastern states of the United States (Allender et al. 2011). A survey in Europe has detected that amphibian ranavirus isolates are

very closely related to those collected from turtles in the same geographical region (Stöhr et al. 2015). A CMTV-like virus was isolated from several Hermann's tortoises (*Testudo hermanni*) that succumbed to systemic disease (Marschang et al. 1999, Price et al. 2017).

Clinical Considerations for Ranaviruses

Some common indicators of ranavirus infections in fish include inflammation, necrosis, circular swimming, abdominal distension, and death (Zilberg et al. 2000). Gross signs in reptiles and amphibians usually present similarly, with focal to extensive hemorrhaging of the internal organs and skin. It is also probable for ranaviruses to cause substantial mortality in younger animals when compared to older ones of the same population (Waltzek et al. 2014).

Ranavirus transmission is possible through direct contact, immersion in water, by fomite, (abiotic object that can transmit infectious agents), and consumption of infected animals (Langdon et al. 1988, Reddacliff and Whittington 1996, Plumb and Zilberg 1999, Woodland et al. 2002, Robert et al. 2011, Brenes et al. 2014). There is good evidence that the main route of transmission from fish to fish is through water (Plumb and Zilberg 1999, Grant et al. 2005). There is mounting evidence that interspecies and interclass transmission plays a substantial role in ranavirus transmission (Brenes et al. 2014, Mao et al. 1999); therefore, it is conceivable that a farmed fish could acquire a disease-causing viral load from an infected fish or even an infected amphibian or reptile that inhabits the same pond. It is also possible that mosquitos transmit ranavirus at least to and from turtles (Kimble et al. 2014).

The transmission of ranavirus infection from a host of a certain vertebrate class to the host of a distinct vertebrate class has been observed in laboratory and wild settings among amphibians, fish, and reptiles (Brenes et al. 2014, Mao et al. 1997). The implications for interclass transmission in numerous and varied environments is therefore far-reaching, as wild and captive amphibians, fish, and reptiles can transmit the virus within shared spaces.

Diagnostic Assessment

Virus isolation can be accomplished with the fathead minnow (FHM) cell line for most ranavirus species, including EHNV, *European sheatfish virus* (ESV), and SCR (Langdon et al. 1986, Ahne et al. 1989, Plumb et al. 1996). Other cell lines such as *epithelioma papulosum cyprini* (EPC), bluegill fry (BF2), and channel catfish ovary (CCO) are also effective and sometimes even recommended based on the species or strain of virus (Pozet et al. 1992). Once the virus is isolated, conventional Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR) can be used to detect the presence of the virus. In fact, qPCR analysis is capable of detecting exceptionally low viral loads, which can aid in evaluating the significance of the infection (Pallister et al. 2007). Visual confirmation of the sample can be accomplished by electron microscopy to identify whether the virion, or virus particle, belongs to the viral family *Iridoviridae* (Burton et al. 2008). Histopathology is not a conclusive way to diagnose a ranavirus infection. Epizootic hematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNV) in fish and all ranaviruses in amphibians are reportable to the Office International des Epizooties (OIE). To diagnose an infection, the OIE recommends immunostaining, antigen-capture ELISA, immunoelectron microscopy, or PCR after cell culture.

Treatment

There is no commercial ranavirus vaccine currently available, although a number of studies have focused on vaccine development (Oh et al. 2014; Zhang et al. 2012). Prevention is the most effective method of controlling infections. Until a vaccine is available, the most effective method to manage infections for these viruses in fish may be temperature therapy, as the effect of ranavirus infection varies with temperature. Adult redfin perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) in 12-21°C water baths died and those in 6-10°C water baths survived with minimal infections (Whittington and Reddacliff 1995). Similarly, rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) mortality

peaked at 20°C and decreased as temperature decreased (Ariel and Jensen 2009). Ranaviruses tend to increase in virulence as temperature increases and mortality appears to cease at a certain low temperature limit (less than 15°C) depending on the fish species. (Whittington and Reddacliff 1995; Ariel and Jensen 2009). There is no known effective treatment for ranavirus infections in amphibians or reptiles, and disease tends to be more acute than in fish (Brenes et al. 2014).

Prevention of Spread

Standard biosecurity procedures are available for review from USDA-Southern Regional Aquaculture Center (USDA-SRAC) publications 4707, 4708, and 4712 (<https://fisheries.tamu.edu>). Transmission of ranavirus can be controlled by eliminating ingress and egress of susceptible species to and from captive and wild environments. Anyone who handles the animals, or the aquaculture systems that contain them, should wear disposable gloves and discard them prior to handling susceptible animals or their environments. Interclass transmission is not only possible, but it can even cause 100% mortality in certain hosts so quarantining animals upon arrival to facilities should be a priority (Moody and Owens 1994). Additionally, ranavirus transmission between animals of different ectothermic vertebrate classes is possible through water (Brenes et al. 2014)

Ranaviruses are emerging disease-causing viruses that pose a significant risk to wild and captive ectothermic species, although they do not currently present a threat to humans and other warm-blooded animals. Although this group of viruses was discovered in the mid 1960's (Granoff et al. 1965), more than 90% of the cases have been discovered in the past decade (Duffus et al. 2015), and the extremely high prevalence of ranaviral disease in reptiles and amphibians alone in wild mortality and morbidity events has been highlighted in Green et al. 2006.

CHAPTER 2
GENOMIC SEQUENCING OF RANAVIRUS ISOLATES FROM THREE-SPINED
STICKLEBACKS (*GASTEROSTEUS ACULEATUS*) AND RED-LEGGED FROGS (*RANA
AURORA*)

Frog virus 3 (FV3), the type species of the genus *Ranavirus*, is a double-stranded DNA virus capable of infecting fish, amphibians, and reptiles (Duffus et al. 2015). Like the other described ranaviruses, FV3 strains are emerging pathogens that can cause rapid mortality events in cohabiting species (Peiffer et al. 2019). In 1996, routine health monitoring was performed on various animals within the Redwood National Park in California. Several dead or moribund three-spined sticklebacks and northern red-legged frogs were collected and submitted to the Maryland Animal Health Diagnostic Laboratory for analysis (Mao et al. 1999). Reddening of the skin, lethargy, and disorientation was observed in some of the three-spined sticklebacks (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) while no clinical or gross signs were observed in the northern red-legged frogs. No microscopic lesions indicative of a ranavirus infection were observed in either species. Stickleback virus (SBV) and tadpole virus 2 (TV2), isolated from tissue pools of three-spined stickleback and northern red-legged frog, respectively, were initially confirmed to be ranaviruses by sequence analysis of the partial major capsid protein sequence. Additional genetic comparison by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis indicated that SBV and TV2 are identical to FV3. In the current study, we report the propagation of the SBV and TV2 isolates followed by phylogenomic characterization through next generation sequencing.

Methods

Cell Culture and Virus Enrichment

The SBV and TV2 samples were maintained for more than 20 years at -80°C by Dr. Chinchar until they were sent to the Wildlife and Aquatic Veterinary Disease Laboratory (WAVDL) at the University of Florida. At WAVDL, the SBV and TV2 isolates were inoculated

onto confluent monolayers of *epithelioma papulosum ciprini* (EPC) cells maintained in L-15 media with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% antibiotic/antifungal at 28°C. The infected cells were monitored daily for cytopathic effect (CPE) for 14 days. The cell culture supernatants were harvested at the third passage and the total DNA was extracted using a DNeasy blood and tissue kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis

DNA sequencing libraries were multiplexed and constructed from the DNA extracts using a Nextera XT DNA kit (Illumina) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Genome sequencing was performed using a V3 chemistry 600-cycle kit on a MiSeq sequencer (Illumina). *De novo* assembly of the paired-end reads was performed in SPAdes v3.12.0 (Bankevich et al. 2012), using default parameters. The quality of the assemblies of the two isolates was assessed by mapping the reads back to the consensus sequences and visually inspecting the alignment in Qiagen CLC Genomics Workbench v20. Genome Annotation Transfer Utility (GATU) was used to annotate the full genomes of SBV and TV2 with FV3 (GenBank accession no. MG953518) as the reference genome (<https://4virology.net/virology-ca-tools/gatu/>). The genome-wide locally colinear block (LCB) alignments of 46 fully sequenced ranaviruses were generated in Mauve v2.4 with default parameters (Table 2-1). The LCB alignments were then concatenated in Geneious v7 (Kearse et al. 2012) and used in a maximum likelihood (ML) analysis in IQTREE (<http://iqtree.cibiv.univie.ac.at>) with default parameters and 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

Results

Cell Culture and Virus Enrichment

The EPC cultures inoculated with the SBV and TV2 isolates all displayed the same CPE characterized by enlarged, refractile cells that lysed, resulting in plaques within 24 h post-

inoculation (Figure 3-1). Destruction of the monolayer was observed within 72 h post-inoculation.

Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis

De novo assembly of the paired-end reads produced contiguous consensus sequences of 105,673 bp and 105,671 bp with a G+C contents of 55% each for SBV and TV2, respectively. Ninety-seven putative ORFs were predicted in both SBV and TV2. Genome analysis in Mauve showed that the two genomes, SBV and TV2, are collinear and virtually identical (99.99%; 105673/105671 nucleotides), except for a two-nucleotide (-CA-) addition in an intergenic repeat region in the former. The ML phylogenetic analysis showed the two isolates of this study are a unique clade within the FV3 subclade and supported them as FV3 strains (Figure 2-2). The complete genome sequences of SBV and TV2 have been deposited in GenBank under the accession nos. MZ514903 and MZ514904, respectively. Raw sequence data of SBV and TV2 have been deposited in Sequence Read Archive (SRA) databases under accession nos. SRR15339644 and SRR15339645, respectively.

Discussion

This study confirms that the SBV and TV2 isolates, from two vertebrate species of distinct classes in a wild setting, as reported in Mao et al. 1999, are identical and demonstrates that full genome analysis allows for the accurate comparison of viral relatedness. The virus in this study exhibited low host specificity, as vertebrate animals from different classes were indeed infected by two virtually identical strains. Furthermore, genome analysis revealed the presence of US22 gene (ORF57) which has only been encoded by CMTV-like ranaviruses such as ADRV (ORF50; GenBank acc. KF033124) and RCV-Z (ORF48; GenBank acc. MF187210) as well as the recombinant ranavirus RCV-Z2 (ORF79; GenBank acc. MF187209). Previous phylogenomic analysis suggested that RCV-Z may have acquired this cellular US22 ortholog from its bullfrog

host before vertically passing the gene along to ADRV, its closest relative, and donating the gene through recombination to RCV-Z2 (Claytor et al. 2017). More sequencing must be completed in order to understand the epidemiology of ranaviruses. The potential impact of FV3 is exceptional as strains are capable of infecting hosts from different vertebrate classes that are staples of global trade and others of conservation concern. Regulatory policies should also be updated to combat the promiscuous nature of these pathogens, so that their effect on aquaculture and wildlife is mitigated.

Table 2-1. Virus abbreviations, names, and GenBank accession numbers of the ranaviruses used in the phylogenetic analysis.

Virus species	Isolate name (abbreviation)	GenBank Acc. No.
<i>Frog virus 3</i>	Frog virus 3 (FV3)	AY548484
	Frog virus 3 isolate SSME (SSME)	KJ175144
	Trioceros melleri ranavirus 1 (TMRV1)	MG953519
	Trioceros melleri ranavirus 2 (TMRV2)	MG953520
	Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus (TCCRv)	MG953518
	Frog virus 3 isolate Op/2015/Netherland (FV3-Op/2015)	MF360246
	Rana nigromaculata ranavirus (RNRV)	MG791866
	Soft-shelled turtle iridovirus (STIV)	EU627010
	Rana grylio iridovirus (RGV)	JQ654586
	Stickleback virus isolate 1096 (SBV)	MZ514903
	Tadpole virus 2 (TV2)	MZ514904
	Tiger frog virus (TFV-China)	AF389451
	Tiger frog virus isolate AV9803 (TFV-1998)	MT512504
	Tiger frog virus isolate F0207 (TFV-F0207)	MT512501
	Tiger frog virus isolate F2112 (TFV-F2112)	MT512503
	Tiger frog virus isolate D11-067 (TFV-D11-067)	MT512498
	Tiger frog virus isolate VD-16-006 (TFV-VD-16-006)	MT512499
	Tiger frog virus isolate VD-17-007 (TFV-VD-17-007)	MT512500
	Tiger frog virus isolate D03-034 (TFV-D03-034)	MT512497
	Tiger frog virus isolate D2008 (TFV-D2008)	MT512502
Bohle iridovirus (BIV)	KX185156	
Zoo ranavirus isolate 040414 (ZRV)	MK227779	
German gecko ranavirus (GGRV)	KP266742	
<i>Ambystoma tigrinum virus</i>	Ambystoma tigrinum virus (ATV)	AY150217
<i>Epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus</i>	Epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNv)	FJ433873
	European sheatfish virus (ESV)	JQ724856
<i>Common midwife toad virus</i>	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-E)	JQ231222
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-NL)	KP056312
	Testudo hermanni ranavirus (THRV-CH8/96)	KP266741
	Tortoise ranavirus isolate 1 (ToRV1)	KP266743
	Andrias davidianus ranavirus (ADRV)	KC865735
	Andrias davidianus ranavirus (ADRV-2010SX)	KF033124
	Chinese giant salamander iridovirus (CGSIV-HN1104)	KF512820
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Lv/2015)	MF004272
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Pe/2015)	MF125269

Table 2-1. Continued

Virus species	Isolate name (abbreviation)	GenBank Acc. No.
<i>Common midwife toad virus</i>	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Pe/2016)	MF125270
	Rana catesbeiana virus isolate RC-Z (RCV-Z)	MF187210
	Rana esculenta virus (REV)	MF538628
	Pelophylax esculentus virus (PEV)	MF538627
	Pike-perch iridovirus (PIIV)	KX574341
<i>European North Atlantic ranavirus</i>	Ranavirus maximus (Rmax)	KX574343
	Cod iridovirus (CoIV)	KX574342
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate F140-16 (LMRV-F140-16)	MH665359
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate F24-15 (LMRV-F24-15)	MH665358
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate V4955 (LMRV-V4955)	MH665360
Unclassified	Short-finned eel ranavirus (SERV)	KX353311

Figure 2-1. Microscopic examination of cytopathic effect (CPE) characteristics of TV2 in the EPC cell line at 28°C. (A) Control flask 24 h post infection (pi). 40x. (B) Infected flask 24 h pi showing enlarged refractile cells and plaques. 40x. (C) Control flask 72 h pi. 100x. (D) Infected flask 72 h pi showing dissolution of the cellular monolayer and sloughed, refractile cells floating in the media. 100x. Scale bar is 100 μ m.

Table 2-2. Predicted open reading frames for the genomes of SBV and TV2.

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
1	1- 771	256	putative replicating factor [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031579
2	1378- 2322	314	putative myristylated membrane [Frog virus 3]	99.7	AIX94574
3	2363- 3199	278	hypothetical protein [Rana grylio iridovirus]	100	AFG73045
4	3129- 4445	438	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46764
5	4485- 4667	60	hypothetical protein FV3gorf4R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031582
6	5550- 5936	128	hypothetical protein FV3gorf7R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031585
7	6028- 9909	1293	DNA-dependent RNA polymerase II largest subunit [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46767
8	10278- 13124	948	putative NTPase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031587
9	13140- 13553	137	hypothetical protein FV3gorf10R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031588
10	13903- 14115	70	hypothetical protein FV3gorf11R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031589
11	14181- 15074	297	hypothetical protein FV3gorf12L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031590
12	15615- 15821	68	hypothetical protein FV3gorf13R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031591
13	15836- 16195	119	hypothetical protein FV3gorf14R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031592
14	16291- 17259	322	AAA-ATPase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031593

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
15	17539- 18366	275	putative integrase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031594
16	18607- 20115	502	hypothetical protein FV3gorf17L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031595
17	20153- 20389	78	hypothetical protein FV3gorf18L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031596
18	20441- 23065	874	surface protein [Frog virus 3]	99.8	QDZ44488
19	23113- 23559	148	hypothetical protein D1R28_gp022 [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506680
20	23782- 24441	219	ISKNV orf56L protein-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26100
21	24571- 27492	973	putative D5 family NTPase/ATPase [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ44398
22	27870- 29018	382	hypothetical protein [Frog virus 3]	100	ASH99205
23	29402- 30499	365	hypothetical protein RUK13gorf24R [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94589
24	30693- 31481	262	hypothetical protein [Rana esculenta virus]	99.6	ASQ42931
25	31548- 31778	76	truncated putative e1F-2alpha-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031604
26	32308- 35220	970	tyrosine kinase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46786
27	35269- 35757	162	hypothetical protein D1R28_gp030 [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506688
28	35936- 36232	98	hypothetical protein FV3gorf29L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031607
29	36434- 36586	50	transmembrane domain protein [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ45977

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
30	36648- 37067	139	hypothetical protein FV3gorf31R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031609
31	37117- 39276	719	neurofilament triplet H1-like protein [Frog virus 3]	94.1	QDZ44592
32	39359- 39550	63	hypothetical protein A190_gp095 [European catfish virus]	100	YP_006347686
33	39695- 40015	106	L-protein-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031612
34	40107- 40568	153	hypothetical protein SSMEgorf35L [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26114
35	40581- 41213	210	hypothetical protein RUK13gorf36L [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94599
36	41609- 42244	211	putative NIF/NLI interacting factor [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031615
37	42385- 44082	565	ribonucleoside diphosphate reductase alpha subunit barrel domain [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031616
38	44188- 44538	116	putative hydrolase of the metallo-beta-lactamase superfamily [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031617
39	44627- 45175	182	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.5	AWU46799
40	45557- 49054	1165	RRV orf2-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	AYP19491
41	49550- 49807	85	hypothetical protein FV3gorf42L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031620
42	50107- 50292	61	hypothetical protein FV3gorf44R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031622
43	50568- 50978	136	hypothetical protein A190_gp105 [European catfish virus]	100	YP_006347696
44	51032- 51472	146	neurofilament triplet H1-like protein [Frog virus 3]	83.6	QKO01787

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
45	51597- 52013	138	hypothetical protein ToRV1_ORF50R [Tortoise ranavirus]	100	AJR29281
46	52016- 52267	83	hypothetical protein FV3gorf48L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031626
47	52376- 53947	523	LCDV1 orf58-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ45061
48	54027- 55712	561	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46809
49	55969- 57036	355	3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase [Rana grylio virus 9506]	100	ABI36881
50	57374- 58942	522	orf20-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031631
51	59173- 59403	76	putative nuclear calmodulin-binding protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031632
52	59441- 60736	431	DEXDc superfamily helicase-like protein [Andrias davidianus ranavirus]	99.1	AGV20585
53	59585- 60724	379	40 kDa protein [Rana catesbeiana virus]	98.4	API65364
54	60930- 61331	133	hypothetical protein [Andrias davidianus ranavirus]	100	AGV20583
55	61375- 62871	498	phosphotransferase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46816
56	63326- 63880	184	hypothetical protein [Common midwife toad virus]	100	ASH98974
57	64462- 65100	212	US22 family protein [Rana catesbeiana virus 2]	99.1	ASU44207
58	65498- 66556	352	hypothetical protein [Common midwife toad virus]	99.4	ASH98867
59	66718- 69759	1013	DNA polymerase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.9	AWU46820

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
60	69768- 69950	60	hypothetical protein FV3gorf61L [Frog virus 3]	98.3	YP_031640
61	70397- 74062	1221	DNA-dependent RNA polymerase II second largest subunit domain 6,7,3,2 beta subunit [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031641
62	74441- 74935	164	putative dUTPase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031642
63	75060- 75347	95	ACrystal structure of CARD-only protein in frog virus 3 [Frog virus 3]	100	6J52_A
64	75740- 75904	54	hypothetical protein D1U33_gp043 [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508671
65	75901- 76452	183	hypothetical protein FV3gorf66L [Frog virus 3]	99.5	YP_031645
66	76507- 77670	387	ribonucleoside diphosphate reductase beta subunit-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031646
67	77951- 78238	95	hypothetical protein FV3gorf68R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031647
68	78374- 78640	88	hypothetical protein [Rana nigromaculata ranavirus]	100	AVM86140
69	78658- 79032	124	hypothetical protein FV3gorf70R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031649
70	79072- 79305	77	hypothetical protein FV3gorf71R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031650
71	79362- 80078	238	hypothetical protein FV3gorf72L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031651
72	80512-81486/ 80510-81484	324	putative NTPase/helicase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031652
73	81661-82773/ 81659-82771	370	hypothetical protein FV3gorf74L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031653
74	82805-83059/ 82803-83057	84	lipopolysaccharide-induced TNF-alpha factor (LITAF)-like protein [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508660

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
75	83122-83343/ 83120-83341	73	hypothetical protein FV3gorf76R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031655
76	83340-83687/ 83338-83685	115	hypothetical protein D1U33_gp030 [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508658
77	84272-84910/ 84270-84908	212	hypothetical protein FV3gorf78L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031657
78	85046-86764/ 85044-86762	572	putative ATPase-dependent protease [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94632
79	87387-88502/ 87385-88500	371	ribonuclease III [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031659
80	88558-88836/ 88556-88834	92	transcription elongation factor SII [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031660
81	88965-89438/ 88963-89436	157	immediate early protein ICP-18 [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031661
82	89888-90532/ 89886-90530	214	cytosine DNA methyltransferase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031662
83	90904-91641/ 90902-91639	245	proliferating cell nuclear antigen [Pike-perch iridovirus]	100	ANZ56939
84	91716-92303/ 91714-92301	195	putative deoxynucleoside kinase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031664
85	92693-92908/ 92691-92906	71	hypothetical protein [Red-eared slider ranavirus]	91.5	QJU69599
86	93261-95078/ 93259-95076	605	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46855
87	95111-95563/ 95109-95561	150	ERV1/ALR-related protein [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506749
88	95631-96713/ 95629-96711	360	surface protein [Frog virus 3]	99.7	QDZ44729
89	96806-98197/ 96804-98195	463	major capsid protein [Frog virus 3]	100	ACP19256

Table 2-2. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
90	98321-99508/ 98319-99506	395	immediate early protein ICP-46 [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46848
91	99891-100136/ 99889-100134	81	hypothetical protein SSMEgorf92R [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26168
92	100318-100485/ 100316-100483	55	hypothetical protein FV3gorf93L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031672
93	100595-101062/ 100593-101060	155	P8.141C-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031673
94	101155-102246/ 101153-102244	363	putative DNA repair protein [Soft-shelled turtle iridovirus]	100	ACF42318
95	103048-103719/ 103046-103717	223	hypothetical protein FV3gorf96R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031675
96	103802-104215/ 103800-104213	137	putative myeloid cell leukemia protein [Soft-shelled turtle iridovirus]	100	ACF42321
97	104780-105445/ 104778-105443	221	US22 family protein [Frog virus 3]	99.5	QKO01838

^aORF72 features two values for Position (nt range) due to a two bp repeat in the intergenic region between ORF70 and ORF71

** ORF72 through ORF97 have two values for Position (nt range) due to the difference in genomes listed above

Abbreviations: aa, amino acids; nt, nucleotides; % ID, percentage identity

Figure 2-2. Maximum-likelihood phylogram depicting the relationship of SBV and TV2 (in red) to 44 other ranaviruses based on the concatenated genome-wide locally collinear block alignments. The bootstrap values are provided at each node.

CHAPTER 3 PHYLOGENOMIC CHARACTERIZATION OF A RANAVIRUS FROM A MORTALITY EVENT IN NORTH CAROLINA

Ranaviruses are double-stranded DNA viruses (Goorha and Murti 1982) that possess numerous virus replication and host immune suppression factors, enabling them to be effectively infectious and lethal (Eaton et al. 2007). Although numerous reports have been published on mortalities caused by ranaviral disease, few have been published on interclass or even interspecies transmission in the wild. As noted in Chapter 2, certain strains of frog virus 3 are capable of infecting cohabiting animals of different vertebrate classes, even in wild settings. Even though the disease or the transmission itself between the two animals of the previous study was not fully experimented upon, this study attempts to demonstrate—through the use of qPCR, *in situ* hybridization, and genome sequencing—that the same strain of ranavirus not only infected animals of different vertebrate classes, but also caused demonstrable disease. Ranavirus transmission has been previously described between amphibians and reptiles in an experimental setting (Brenes et al. 2014); however, this would be the first report of the same strain of ranavirus causing disease in cohabiting amphibians and reptiles in a wild setting, to the author’s knowledge. The tissue samples used in this study were provided by the North Carolina Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory System (NCVDLS). In the current study, we report the phylogenomic characterization of ranaviruses through next generation sequencing and detection of ranaviral nucleic acid in host tissues by ISH using RNAscope® technology.

Methods

Case History

In May of 2020, employees of Blue Jay Point County Park in North Carolina observed a mass mortality event of tadpoles of unknown species (*Rana sp.*) and eastern painted turtles (*Chrysemys picta picta*) cohabiting an outdoor manmade pond over the course of 2 weeks. At

least six turtles and 50 tadpoles were found dead and no clinical signs were reported by the park personnel. Four eastern painted turtles and four unidentified tadpoles were submitted to the North Carolina Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory System (NCVDLS) for necropsy. Of the four turtles, only two were necropsied and only one, WVL20057-2, presented with gross lesions: a pale-yellow liver with occasional white foci. The gross examination also revealed moderate autolysis and freezing artifact in the turtle that was submitted for examination (WVL20057-3). No significant gross lesions were observed in the four tadpoles.

Histopathology

The coelomic cavities of one tadpole of unknown species, WVL20057-5, and one eastern painted turtle, WVL20057-3, were incised and the body immersed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 hr and 70% ethanol directly after. Immersion for 48-96 hr in 0.5 M Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) pH buffered to 8.0 (Fisher BioReagents) decalcified the tadpole and turtle tissue. Processing of fixed tissues by embedding, sectioning, and hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was then completed and the prepared slides were examined for histopathology.

Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)

Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR) was utilized to confirm the presence of ranavirus nucleic acid in DNA extracted from the tissues of the turtles (WVL20057-2, WVL20057-3, WVL20057-4) and the tadpole (WVL20057-5). To screen for ranavirus by qPCR, DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit from 200 μ L of pooled tissue homogenates according to the manufacturer' instructions. A 97 bp region of the ranavirus major capsid protein was targeted by the TaqMan qPCR to detect the level of infection by calculating viral copy number as previously described (Leung et al. 2017, Stilwell et al. 2018). The TaqMan® Fast Universal PCR Master Mix 2X (Applied Biosystems) was used to prepare the

qPCR assay with QIAgility™ (Qiagen). Each sample for qPCR contained a solution including 4 µL of 12.5 ng µL⁻¹ of nucleic acid template, 0.36 µM of forward and reverse primers, 0.1 µM of probe, 10 µL of universal qPCR master mix (TaqMan® Fast Universal PCR Master Mix 2X, Applied Biosystems), and 3 µL of molecular-grade water for a total of 20 µL. The samples were run on a QuantStudio 5 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) using the following fast qPCR protocol thermocycling conditions: 95°C for 20 s followed by 40 cycles at 95°C for 3 s and 60°C for 30 s. A sample was considered positive if the 6-carboxy-X-rhodamine (ROX)-normalized 6-carboxyfluorescein (FAM) signal exceeded the cycle threshold (Ct) assigned by the Applied Biosystems software. Samples were run in triplicate with one Xeno internal positive control well (VetMAX™ Xeno™ Internal Positive Control (IPC) – VIC™ Assay). A 10-fold dilution series of FV3 MCP linearized plasmid DNA (10⁷-10¹ copies) was amplified in triplicate on the plate to function as a standard for estimating the viral copy number. Two no template controls (molecular-grade water) were run in addition to the other material. 50 µL Polyolefin films (Applied Biosystems) were used to seal the polypropylene 96-well plates (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies). QuantStudio 5 Real-Time PCR software (Applied Biosystems) estimated the threshold of detection (Ct) and the number of viral copies in real-time. Samples were considered FV3-positive when at least two of the three of the triplicate samples yielded a Ct value of ≤40.

RNAscope® *In Situ* Hybridization (ISH)

In situ hybridization (ISH) was completed to corroborate the histopathological and molecular findings of this study. A manual *in situ* hybridization (ISH) assay using RNAscope® technology was used to detect ranavirus nucleic acid in formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) heart, stomach, intestine, and liver tissues from the turtle (WVL20057-3) and the whole tadpole. Specific probes were designed by Advanced Cell Diagnostics (Newark, California),

based on the following genes: dihydrodipicolinate reductase gene (DapB; negative control probe) [catalog # 312038] and the FV3 MCP gene (V-FV3-orf90R; test probe) [catalog # 439991]. Formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue sections were sectioned at 5 µm and then mounted onto Superfrost™ Plus glass slides (Fisherbrand™). Mounted tissue slides were prepared for the RNAscope® ISH by drying at 60°C for 1 hr (HybEZ™ Oven, ACD) prior to conducting the RNAscope® assay, as per the manufacturer's instructions. All equipment and reagents were prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. The RNAscope® 2.5 HD RED Reagent Kit was employed to complete the ISH assay (ACD). Each run of the ISH assay included an FV3-positive (Stilwell 2017) control slide and a procedural negative (bacterial DapB) control slide in addition to the slides from the necropsied animals. The steps taken, according to the manufacturer's instructions, are as follows (Wang et al. 2012): 1) sample deparaffinization and dehydration; 2) tissue section pretreatments; 3) target probe hybridization; 4) signal amplification; 5) signal detection; 6) counterstaining, and 7) slide mounting.

Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis

DNA sequencing libraries were constructed from the DNA extracts using a sparQ DNA library prep Kit (Quantabio). Genome sequencing was performed using a V3 chemistry 600-cycle kit on a MiSeq sequencer (Illumina) and SP reagent kit on a NovaSeq 6000 sequencer (Illumina) for sample WVL20057-3 and sample WVL20057-5, respectively. De novo assembly of the paired-end reads was performed in SPAdes v3.12.0 (Bankevich et al. 2012), using default parameters. The quality of the assemblies of the two strains was assessed by mapping the reads back to the consensus sequences and visually inspecting the alignment in Qiagen CLC Genomics Workbench v20. Genome Annotation Transfer Utility (GATU) was used to annotate the full genomes of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 with FV3 (GenBank accession no. MG953518) as the reference genome (<https://4virology.net/virology-ca-tools/gatu/>). The genome-wide locally

colinear block (LCB) alignments of 48 fully sequenced ranaviruses were generated in Mauve v2.4 with default parameters (Table 3-1). The LCB alignments were then concatenated in Geneious v7 (Kearse et al. 2012) and used in a maximum likelihood (ML) analysis in IQTREE (<http://iqtree.cibiv.univie.ac.at>) with default parameters and 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

Results

Histopathology

Examination of the histology slides revealed chronic inflammation and granulomas in the central nervous system (CNS) of the tadpole. The eastern painted turtle (WVL20057-3) presented with aggregates of mixed leukocytes in the epicardium, infiltration with mixed leukocytes in and necrosis of the intestine, aggregates of leukocytes in the interstitium of the kidney, and necrosis of hepatocytes in the liver.

Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)

Numerical results for the qPCR are provided below in Table 3-2. Although only two samples out of the four were used for genome sequencing, all of them were positive based on the mean cycle threshold (Ct) values reported (Table 3-2). According to the Applied Biosystems software, the qPCR was 96.61% efficient, demonstrating the usefulness of running triplicate samples and effective reagents, including the primers (Leung et al. 2017, Svec et al. 2015).

RNAscope® *In Situ* Hybridization (ISH)

WVL20057-3 was selected out of the three turtle samples for further analysis due to the high viral copy number and low Ct value reported by qPCR. WVL20057-5 was utilized because it was the only tadpole sample available. RNAscope® ISH labeling from one turtle (WVL20057-3) and one tadpole identified ranaviral nucleic acid in tissues including the stomach and CNS, respectively (Figure 3-3). There was also significant staining in the developing limb bud of the

tadpole. No labeling was observed when the negative control probe was applied to the same tissue sections of either animal (Figure 3-3).

Complete Genome Sequencing, Annotation, and Phylogenetic analysis

De novo assembly of the paired-end reads in SPAdes (Bankevich et al. 2012) produced contiguous consensus sequences of 106,024 bp and 105,988 bp with G+C contents of 55% each for WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5, respectively. Ninety-six putative ORFs were predicted in both WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5. Genome analysis in Mauve showed that the two genomes, WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5, are collinear and identical (99.97%; 106,024/105,988 nucleotides), except for two repeats of a single 18 bp sequence in a predicted neurofilament H1 gene (Figure 3-2). The ML phylogenetic analysis supported WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 within the FV3 subclade as FV3 strains. In addition, these two form a sister clade with the two isolates described in Chapter 2 (Figure 3-3).

Discussion

The results from this study revealed that the ranaviral strains from the tadpole and turtle are nearly identical and ranavirus nucleic acid was localized to the tissues of the virus infected animals. Furthermore, according to the phylogenomic analysis, the two pairs of strains from Chapters 2 and 3 belong to the same subclade (i.e., FV3) and the two pairs form a unique clade. After the findings of Mao in 1999, Brenes et al. in 2014, and Peiffer et al. in 2019, Chapter 3 of this work complements the growing wealth of knowledge of interclass transmission of FV3.

Results from histopathology were limited and not necessarily consistent with ranavirus infections in the respective host animals. For example, chronic inflammation and granuloma formation are not common findings with ranavirus infections in tadpoles. Conversely, leukocyte aggregation and necrosis in organs such as the intestine, kidney, and liver are not uncommon findings (Johnson et al. 2008). Because of the apparent lack of clinical and gross pathology

leading up to death, the infection of the tadpoles and turtles in this case displayed an insidious course. Acute mortality, as observed in the animals affected in North Carolina, can be common, especially if there is no regular surveillance of disease or clinical signs (Brenes et al. 2014). Lesions identified during histologic identification, such as hepatic necrosis, are known to present in the host animals of this study, although there are many other gross signs of ranavirus disease not seen in this case (De Voe et al. 2004). Additionally, there are some gross signs seen in the animals of this study that are not consistent with ranaviral disease. It is worth noting that ranavirus infection can present with a broad range of clinical and gross signs, especially in cases with coinfections (Miller et al. 2008, Souza et al. 2012). Chronic inflammation as well as granuloma formation in the central nervous system of the tadpole has been reported before (De Jesús et al. 2016); however, the positive staining surrounding the granulomas in the tadpole CNS is possibly the result of non-specific binding. Accurate histopathology was marred by the sporadic collection, storage, and shipment of animals in ice, as the tissues exhibit widespread autolysis and freeze-thaw artifact. Despite the autolysis and freeze-thaw artifact, the ISH assay still functioned and returned positive results.

Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction was instrumental in the diagnostic aspects of this study, as presence of ranavirus DNA was identified in extracted DNA concentrations as low as 2 ng/ μ L in the WVL20057-5. qPCR also allowed us to select the most effective samples for further study on the presupposition of high viral copy number and low Ct value leading to more effective ISH and genome sequencing. Genome sequencing revealed two genomes within a typical genome size range and %G+C for frog virus 3 as previously described (Tan et al. 2004). Both genomes had a G+C content of 55%. Similar to SBV and TV2, FV3 strains WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 possess a CMTV-like US22 gene, in place of an FV3-like US22 (ORF5) that

is common to all members of the FV3 subclade- The same CMTV-like US22 gene has also been discovered in *Trioceros melleri* ranavirus 1 (TMRV1), *Trioceros melleri* ranavirus 2 (TMRV2), and *Terrapene carolina carolina* ranavirus (TCCRv) from the Maryland Zoo in Baltimore (Peiffer et al. 2019). Interestingly, these seven genomes that exhibit the lowest host specificity appear to form a unique clade within the FV3 subclade. The presence of CMTV-like US22 is one of the shared derived characteristics among the seven genomes. The clinical significance of US22 in these two cases is unknown; however, studies have found that it may be involved with combating host antiviral response (Zhang et al. 2011).

Finally, due to the seemingly acute mortality observed in the latter study and the persistence of viral infections in natural settings, it is important to conduct regular health assessments on wild animals. Many future experiments can be performed to further our understanding of these potentially deadly and widespread viruses; challenge studies utilizing these strains could be completed in order to conclusively establish interclass transmission between amphibian and reptile and amphibian and fish. It is apparent that ranavirus disease can be insidious, as there were no reports of clinical or gross signs of disease in advance of the mortality observed in the tadpoles and turtles.

Table 3-1. Virus abbreviations, names, and GenBank accession numbers of the ranaviruses used in the phylogenetic analysis.

Virus species	Isolate name (abbreviation)	GenBank Acc. No.
<i>Frog virus 3</i>	Frog virus 3 (FV3)	AY548484
	Frog virus 3 isolate SSME (SSME)	KJ175144
	Trioceros melleri ranavirus 1 (TMRV1)	MG953519
	Trioceros melleri ranavirus 2 (TMRV2)	MG953520
	Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus (TCCRv)	MG953518
	Frog virus 3 isolate Op/2015/Netherlands (FV3-Op/2015)	MF360246
	Rana nigromaculata ranavirus (RNRV)	MG791866
	Soft-shelled turtle iridovirus (STIV)	EU627010
	Rana grylio iridovirus (RGV)	JQ654586
	Stickleback virus isolate 1096 (SBV)	MZ514903
	Tadpole virus 2 (TV2)	MZ514904
	Frog virus 3 strain WV20057-3	N/A
	Frog virus 3 strain WV20057-5	N/A
	Tiger frog virus (TFV-China)	AF389451
	Tiger frog virus isolate AV9803 (TFV-1998)	MT512504
	Tiger frog virus isolate F0207 (TFV-F0207)	MT512501
	Tiger frog virus isolate F2112 (TFV-F2112)	MT512503
	Tiger frog virus isolate D11-067 (TFV-D11-067)	MT512498
	Tiger frog virus isolate VD-16-006 (TFV-VD-16-006)	MT512499
	Tiger frog virus isolate VD-17-007 (TFV-VD-17-007)	MT512500
	Tiger frog virus isolate D03-034 (TFV-D03-034)	MT512497
	Tiger frog virus isolate D2008 (TFV-D2008)	MT512502
	Bohle iridovirus (BIV)	KX185156
	Zoo ranavirus isolate 040414 (ZRV)	MK227779
	German gecko ranavirus (GGRV)	KP266742
	<i>Ambystoma tigrinum virus</i>	Ambystoma tigrinum virus (ATV)
<i>Epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus</i>	Epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNv)	FJ433873
	European sheatfish virus (ESV)	JQ724856
<i>Common midwife toad virus</i>	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-E)	JQ231222
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-NL)	KP056312
	Testudo hermanni ranavirus (THRv-CH8/96)	KP266741
	Tortoise ranavirus isolate 1 (ToRV1)	KP266743
	Andrias davidianus ranavirus (ADRV)	KC865735
	Andrias davidianus ranavirus (ADRV-2010SX)	KF033124
Chinese giant salamander iridovirus (CGSIV-HN1104)	KF512820	

Table 3-1. Continued

Virus species	Isolate name (abbreviation)	GenBank Acc. No.
<i>Common midwife toad virus</i>	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Lv/2015)	MF004272
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Pe/2015)	MF125269
	Common midwife toad virus (CMTV-Pe/2016)	MF125270
	Rana catesbeiana virus isolate RC-Z (RCV-Z)	MF187210
	Rana esculenta virus (REV)	MF538628
	Pelophylax esculentus virus (PEV)	MF538627
	Pike-perch iridovirus (PIIV)	KX574341
<i>European North Atlantic ranavirus</i>	Ranavirus maximus (Rmax)	KX574343
	Cod iridovirus (CoIV)	KX574342
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate F140-16 (LMRV-F140-16)	MH665359
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate F24-15 (LMRV-F24-15)	MH665358
	Lumpfish ranavirus isolate V4955 (LMRV-V4955)	MH665360
Unclassified	Short-finned eel ranavirus (SERV)	KX353311

Figure 3-1. Figure Histology and RNAscope® *in situ* hybridization results from turtle and tadpole tissues targeted for ISH. A-C depict H&E-stained slides of turtle gastric mucosa (A), tadpole spinal cord (B), and tadpole limb bud (C). D-F depict tissues processed with dapB negative control probe. G-I depict tissues processed with ranavirus probe. Top row: 200x. Middle and bottom rows: 100x.

Table 3-3. Predicted open reading frames for the genomes of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5.

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
1	1- 771	256	putative replicating factor [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031579
2	1378- 2358	326	putative myristylated membrane [Frog virus 3]	99.7	AIX94574
3	2396- 3235	279	hypothetical protein [Rana grylio iridovirus]	100	AFG73045
4	3165- 4481	438	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46764
5	4522- 4704	60	hypothetical protein FV3gorf4R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031582
6	5587- 5973	128	hypothetical protein FV3gorf7R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031585
7	6065- 9946	1293	DNA-dependent RNA polymerase II largest subunit [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46767
8	10315- 13161	948	putative NTPase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031587
9	13177- 13590	137	hypothetical protein FV3gorf10R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031588
10	13940- 14152	70	hypothetical protein FV3gorf11R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031589
11	14218- 15111	297	hypothetical protein FV3gorf12L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031590
12	15652- 15858	68	hypothetical protein FV3gorf13R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031591
13	15873- 16232	119	hypothetical protein FV3gorf14R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031592
14	16329- 17276	315	AAA-ATPase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031593

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
15	17732- 18382	216	putative integrase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031594
16	18623- 20131	502	hypothetical protein FV3gorf17L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031595
17	20169- 20405	78	hypothetical protein FV3gorf18L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031596
18	20457- 23018	853	surface protein [Frog virus 3]	99.8	QDZ44488
19	23066- 23512	148	hypothetical protein D1R28_gp022 [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506680
20	23735- 24394	219	ISKNV orf56L protein-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26100
21	24524- 27445	973	putative D5 family NTPase/ATPase [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ44398
22	27825- 28973	382	hypothetical protein [Frog virus 3]	100	ASH99205
23	29357- 30454	365	hypothetical protein RUK13gorf24R [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94589
24	30648- 31439	263	hypothetical protein [Rana esculenta virus]	99.6	ASQ42931
25	31506- 31736	76	truncated putative e1F-2alpha-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031604
26	32270- 35182	970	tyrosine kinase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46786
27	35231- 35719	162	hypothetical protein D1R28_gp030 [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506688
28	35898- 36194	98	hypothetical protein FV3gorf29L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031607
29	36396- 36548	50	transmembrane domain protein [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ45977

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
30	36610- 37029	139	hypothetical protein FV3gorf31R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031609
31	37079- 39148	689	neurofilament triplet H1-like protein [Frog virus 3]	94.1	QDZ44592
32	39231- 39422	63	hypothetical protein A190_gp095 [European catfish virus]	100	YP_006347686
33	39566- 39886	106	L-protein-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031612
34	39978- 40439	153	hypothetical protein SSMEgorf35L [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26114
35	40637- 41128	163	hypothetical protein RUK13gorf36L [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94599
36	41523- 42158	211	putative NIF/NLI interacting factor [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031615
37	42299- 43996	565	ribonucleoside diphosphate reductase alpha subunit barrel domain [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031616
38	44102- 44452	116	putative hydrolase of the metallo-beta-lactamase superfamily [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031617
39	44541- 45089	182	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.5	AWU46799
40	45471- 48968	1165	RRV orf2-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	AYP19491
41	49611- 50759	382	hypothetical protein FV3gorf42L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031620
42	50887- 51297	136	hypothetical protein FV3gorf44R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031622
43 ^a	51351-51845/ 51351-51809	164/152	hypothetical protein A190_gp105 [European catfish virus]	100	YP_006347696
44 ^{**}	51970-52386/ 51934-52350	138	neurofilament triplet H1-like protein [Frog virus 3]	83.6	QKO01787

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
45**	52389-52640/ 52353-52604	83	hypothetical protein ToRV1_ORF50R [Tortoise ranavirus]	100	AJR29281
46**	52749-54311/ 52713-54275	520	hypothetical protein FV3gorf48L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031626
47**	54391-56076/ 54355-56040	561	LCDV1 orf58-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	QDZ45061
48**	56333-57400/ 56297-57364	355	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46809
49**	57738-59306/ 57702-59270	522	3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase [Rana grylio virus 9506]	100	ABI36881
50**	59553-59783/ 59517-59747	76	orf20-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031631
51**	59821-61116/ 59785-61080	431	putative nuclear calmodulin-binding protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031632
52**	59965-61104/ 59929-61068	379	DEXDc superfamily helicase-like protein [Andrias davidianus ranavirus]	99.1	AGV20585
53**	61310-61714/ 61274-61678	134	40 kDa protein [Rana catesbeiana virus]	98.4	API65364
54**	61755-63251/ 61719-63215	498	hypothetical protein [Andrias davidianus ranavirus]	100	AGV20583
55**	63703-64257/ 63667-64221	184	phosphotransferase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.8	AWU46816
56**	64948-65586/ 64912-65550	212	hypothetical protein [Common midwife toad virus]	100	ASH98974
57**	65984-67042/ 65948-67006	352	US22 family protein [Rana catesbeiana virus 2]	99.1	ASU44207
58**	67204-70245/ 67168-70209	1013	hypothetical protein [Common midwife toad virus]	99.4	ASH98867
59**	70254-70436/ 70218-70400	60	DNA polymerase [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.9	AWU46820

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
60**	70873-74538/ 70837-74502	1221	hypothetical protein FV3gorf61L [Frog virus 3]	98.3	YP_031640
61**	74917-75411/ 74881-75375	164	DNA-dependent RNA polymerase II second largest subunit domain 6,7,3,2 beta subunit [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031641
62**	75521-75808/ 75485-75772	95	putative dUTPase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031642
63**	76201-76365/ 76165-76329	54	ACrystal structure of CARD-only protein in frog virus 3 [Frog virus 3]	100	6J52_A
64**	76362-76913/ 76326-76877	183	hypothetical protein D1U33_gp043 [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508671
65**	76968-78131/ 76932-78095	387	hypothetical protein FV3gorf66L [Frog virus 3]	99.5	YP_031645
66**	78414-78701/ 78378-78665	95	ribonucleoside diphosphate reductase beta subunit-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031646
67**	78838-79104/ 78802-79068	88	hypothetical protein FV3gorf68R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031647
68**	79122-79496/ 79086-79460	124	hypothetical protein [Rana nigromaculata ranavirus]	100	AVM86140
69**	79536-79769/ 79500-79733	77	hypothetical protein FV3gorf70R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031649
70**	79826-80542/ 79790-80506	238	hypothetical protein FV3gorf71R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031650
71**	80976-81950/ 80940-81914	324	hypothetical protein FV3gorf72L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031651
72**	82125-83237/ 82089-83201	370	putative NTPase/helicase-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031652
73**	83269-83523/ 83233-83487	84	hypothetical protein FV3gorf74L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031653
74**	83586-83807/ 83550-83771	73	lipopolysaccharide-induced TNF-alpha factor (LITAF)-like protein [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508660

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
75**	83804-84151/ 83768-84115	115	hypothetical protein FV3gorf76R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031655
76**	84736-85374/ 84700-85338	212	hypothetical protein D1U33_gp030 [Common midwife toad virus]	100	YP_009508658
77**	85510-87228/ 85474-87192	572	hypothetical protein FV3gorf78L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031657
78**	87851-88966/ 87815-88930	371	putative ATPase-dependent protease [Frog virus 3]	100	AIX94632
79**	89022-89300/ 88986-89264	92	ribonuclease III [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031659
80**	89429-89902/ 89393-89866	157	transcription elongation factor SII [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031660
81**	90352-90996/ 90316-90960	214	immediate early protein ICP-18 [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031661
82**	91368-92105/ 91332-92069	245	cytosine DNA methyltransferase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031662
83**	92180-92767/ 92144-92731	195	proliferating cell nuclear antigen [Pike-perch iridovirus]	100	ANZ56939
84**	93157-93342/ 93121-93306	61	putative deoxynucleoside kinase [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031664
85**	93695-95512/ 93659-95476	605	hypothetical protein [Red-eared slider ranavirus]	91.5	QJU69599
86**	95545-95997/ 95509-95961	150	hypothetical protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46855
87**	96065-97126/ 96029-97090	353	ERV1/ALR-related protein [Bohle iridovirus]	100	YP_009506749
88**	97219-98610/ 97183-98574	463	surface protein [Frog virus 3]	99.7	QDZ44729
89**	98734-99921/ 98698-99885	395	major capsid protein [Frog virus 3]	100	ACP19256

Table 3-3. Continued

ORF	Position (nt range)	Product size (aa)	Best BLAST hit		
			Description	% ID	Accession no.
90**	100241-100486/ 100205-100450	81	immediate early protein ICP-46 [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	100	AWU46848
91**	100668-100835/ 100632-100799	55	hypothetical protein SSMEgorf92R [Frog virus 3]	100	AHM26168
92**	100945-101412/ 100909-101376	155	hypothetical protein FV3gorf93L [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031672
93**	101505-102596/ 101469-102560	363	P8.141C-like protein [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031673
94**	103400-104071/ 103364-104035	223	putative DNA repair protein [Soft-shelled turtle iridovirus]	100	ACF42318
95**	104154-104567/ 104118-104531	137	hypothetical protein FV3gorf96R [Frog virus 3]	100	YP_031675
96**	105131-105796/ 105095-105760	221	US22 family protein [Terrapene carolina carolina ranavirus]	99.6	AWU46854

^aORF43 has two values for ORF length and % ID because WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 diverged in this region. WVL20057-3 contains two additional 18 bp repeats within this ORF that WVL20057-5 does not

**ORF43 through ORF96 have two values for position (nt range) due to the difference in genomes listed above

Abbreviations: aa, amino acids; nt, nucleotides; % ID, percentage identity

Figure 3-3. Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree depicting the relationship of WVL20057-3 and WVL20057-5 (in orange) to 46 other ranaviruses based on the concatenated genome-wide locally colinear block alignments. IQ-TREE was used to create the Maximum Likelihood tree using 1000 bootstraps. See Table 3-1 for the list of ranavirus isolates and abbreviations used in this tree.

LIST OF REFERENCES

- Ahne W, Schlotfeldt HJ, Thomsen I. 1989. Fish viruses: isolation of an icosahedral cytoplasmic deoxyribovirus from sheatfish (*Silurus glanis*). *J Vet Med B* 36:333–336.
- Allender MC, Abd-Eldaim M, Schumacher J, McRuer D, Christian LS, Kennedy M. 2011. PCR prevalence of ranavirus in free-ranging eastern box turtles (*Terrapene carolina carolina*) at rehabilitation centers in three southeastern US states. *J Wildl Dis* 47:759—764.
- Ariel E, Holopainen R, Olesen NJ, Tapiovaara H. 2010. Comparative study of ranavirus isolates from cod (*Gadus morhua*) and turbot (*Psetta maxima*) with reference to other ranaviruses. *Arch Virol* 155:1261–1271.
- Ariel E, Jensen BB. 2009. Challenge studies of European stocks of redbfin perch, *Perca fluviatilis*, and rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss* with epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus. *J Fish Dis* 32(12):1017–1025.
- Bankevich A, Nurk S, Antipov D, Gurevich AA, Dvorkin M, Kulikov AS, Lesin VM, Nikolenko SI, Pham S, Prjibelski AD, Pyshkin AV, Sirotkin AV, Vyahhi N, Tesler G, Alekseyev MA, Pevzner PA. 2012. SPAdes: a new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *J Comput Biol* 19:455–477.
- Brenes R, Gray MJ, Waltzek TB, Wilkes RP, Miller DL. 2014. Transmission of ranavirus between ectothermic vertebrate hosts. *PLoS One* 9:e92476.
- Burton EC, Miller DL, Styer EL, Gray MJ. 2008. Amphibian ocular malformation associated with frog virus 3. *Vet J* 177:442–444.
- Chinchar VG, Hyatt AD, Miyazaki T, Williams T. 2009. Family Iridoviridae: poor viral relations no longer. In Van Etten JL (ed) *Current topics in microbiology and immunology*, vol 328, Lesser-known large dsDNA viruses. Springer, Berlin.
- Clayton SC, Subramaniam K, Landrau-Giovannetti N, Chinchar VG, Gray MJ, Miller DL, Mavian C, Salemi M, Wisely S, Waltzek TB. 2017. Ranavirus phylogenomics: signatures of recombination and inversions among Bullfrog *Rana* culture isolates. *Virology* 511:330–343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2017.07.028>.
- Cordier O, Aubertin AM, Lopez C, Tondre L. 1981. Inhibition de la traduction par le FV3: action des proteines virales de structure solubilisees sur la synthese proteique in vivo et in vitro. *Ann Virol (Inst Pasteur)* 132 E:25–39.
- Cunningham AA, Langton TES, Bennett PM, Drury SE, Gough RE, Kirkwood JK. 1993. Unusual mortality associated with poxvirus-like particles in frogs (*Rana temporaria*). *Vet Rec* 133:141—142.

- De Jesús Andino F, Jones L, Maggirwar SB, Robert J. 2016. Frog virus 3 dissemination in the brain of tadpoles, but not in adult xenopus, involves blood brain barrier dysfunction. *Scientific Reports* 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep22508>.
- De Voe R, Geissler K, Elmore S, Rotstein D, Lewbart G, Guy J. 2004. Ranavirus-associated morbidity and mortality in a group of captive eastern box turtles (*Terrapene carolina carolina*). *Journal of Zoo and Wildlife Medicine* 35:534–543.
- Duffus ALJ, Marschang RE, Waltzek TB, Stöhr A, Allender MC, Gotesman M, Whittington R, Hick P, Hines M. 2015. Distribution and host range of ranaviruses. In Gray MJ, Chinchar VG (eds) *Ranaviruses: lethal pathogens of ectothermic vertebrates*. Springer, Secaucus.
- Eaton HE, Metcalf J, Penny E, Tcherepanov V, Upton C, Brunetti CR. 2007. Comparative genomic analysis of the family Iridoviridae: re-annotating and defining the core set of iridovirus genes. *Virol J* 4:11.
- Geng, Y, Wang KY, Zhou ZY, Li CW, Wang J, He M, Yin ZQ, Lai WM. 2011. First report of a ranavirus associated with morbidity and mortality in farmed Chinese giant salamanders (*Andrias Davidianus*). *J Comp Path* 145:95–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcpa.2010.11.012>.
- Gobbo F, Cappellozza E, Pastore MR, Bovo G. 2010. Susceptibility of black bullhead *Ameiurus melas* to a panel of ranavirus isolates. *Dis Aquat Organ* 90:167–174.
- Goorha R, Murti KG. 1982. The genome of frog virus 3, an animal DNA virus, is circularly permuted and terminally redundant. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 79:248–252.
- Granoff A, Came PE, Rafferty KA. 1965. The isolation and properties of viruses from *Rana pipiens*: their possible relationship to the renal adenocarcinoma of the leopard frog. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 126:237–255.
- Grant EC, Inendino KR, Love WJ, Philipp DP, Goldberg TL. 2005. Effects of practices related to catch-and-release angling on mortality and viral transmission in juvenile largemouth bass infected with largemouth bass virus. *J Aquat Anim Health* 17:315–322.
- Green DE, Converse KA, Schrader AK. 2002. Epizootiology of Sixty-Four Amphibian Morbidity and Mortality Events in the USA, 1996-2001. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 969: 323-339. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2002.tb04400.x>.
- Grizzle JM, Brunner CJ. 2003. Review of largemouth bass virus. *Fisheries* 28:10–14.
- Jancovich JK, Davidson EW, Morado JF, Jacobs BL, Collins JP. 1997. Isolation of a lethal virus from the endangered tiger salamander *Ambystoma tigrinum stebbinsi*. *Dis Aquat Organ* 31:161–167.
- Jensen BB, Ersbøll AK, Ariel E. 2009. Susceptibility of pike (*Esox lucius*) to a panel of Ranavirus isolates. *Dis. Aquat. Organ* 83:169-179.

- Johnson AJ, Pessier AP, Wellehan JFX, Childress A, Norton TM, Stedman NL, Bloom DC, Belzer W, Titus VR, Wagner R, Brooks JW, Spratt J, Jacobson ER. 2008. Ranavirus infection of free-ranging and captive box turtles and tortoises in the United States. *J Wildl Dis* 44:851–863. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7589/0090-3558-44.4.851>.
- Kearse M, Moir R, Wilson A, Stones-Havas S, Cheung M, Sturrock S, Buxton S, Cooper A, Markowitz S, Duran C, Thierer T, Ashton B, Meintjes P, Drummond A. 2012. Geneious Basic: an integrated and extendable desktop software platform for the organization and analysis of sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 28:1647–1649. <https://doi.org/10.1093>.
- Kimble SJ, Karna AK, Johnson AJ, Hoverman JT, Williams RN. 2014. Mosquitoes as a potential vector of ranavirus transmission in terrestrial turtles. *EcoHealth*, 12:334–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10393-014-0974-3>.
- Langdon JS. 1989. Experimental transmission and pathogenicity of epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNV) in redbfin perch, *Perca fluviatilis*, and 11 other teleosts. *J Fish Dis* 12:295–310.
- Langdon JS, Humphrey JD, Williams LM. 1988. Outbreaks of an EHNV-like iridovirus in cultured rainbow trout, *Salmo gairdneri* Richardson, in Australia. *J Fish Dis* 11:93–96.
- Langdon JS, Humphrey JD, Williams LM, Hyatt AD, Westbury HA. 1986. First virus isolation from Australian fish: an iridovirus-like pathogen from redbfin perch, *Perca fluviatilis*. *J Fish Dis* 9:263–268.
- Leung WTM, Thomas-Walters L, Garner TWJ, Balloux F, Durrant C, Price SJ. 2017. A quantitative-PCR based method to estimate ranavirus viral load following normalisation by reference to an ultraconserved vertebrate target. *J Virol Methods* 249:147–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2017.08.016>.
- Mao J, Green DE, Fellers G, Chinchar VG. 1999. Molecular characterization of iridoviruses isolated from sympatric amphibians and fish. *Virus Res* 63:45–52.
- Marschang RE, Becher P, Posthaus H, Wild P, Thiel HJ, Müller-Doblies U, Kalet EF, Bacciarini LN. 1999. Isolation and characterization of an iridovirus from Hermann's tortoises (*Testudo Hermannii*). *Arch Virol* 144:1909–1922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s007050050714>.
- Mazzoni R, José de Mesquita A, Fleury LFF, Diederichsen de Brito WME, Nunes IA, Robert J, Morales H, Coelho ASG, Barthasson DL, Galli L, Catroxo MHB. 2009. Mass mortality associated with frog virus 3-like ranavirus infection in farmed tadpoles, *Rana catesbeiana*, from Brazil. *Dis Aquat Organ* 86:181–191.
- Miller DL, Rajeev S, Brookins M, Cook J, Whittington L, Baldwin CA. 2008. Concurrent infection with ranavirus, *batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*, and *aeromonas* in a captive Anuran Colony. *J Zoo Wildl Med* 39:445–449. <https://doi.org/10.1638/2008-0012.1>.

- Miller DL, Rajeev S, Gray MJ, Baldwin CA. 2007. Frog virus 3 infection, cultured American bullfrogs. *Emerg Infect Dis* 13:342-3.
- Moody NJG, Owens L. 1994. Experimental demonstration of pathogenicity of a frog virus, Bohle iridovirus, for fish species, barramundi *Lates calcefer*. *Dis Aquat Organ* 18:95–102.
- Murali S, Wu MF, Guo IC, Chen SC, Yang HW, Chang CY. 2002. Molecular characterization and pathogenicity of a grouper iridovirus (GIV) isolated from yellow grouper, *Epinephelus awoara*. *J Fish Dis* 25:91–100.
- Oh SY, Oh MJ, Nishizawa T. 2014. Potential for a live red seabream iridovirus (RSIV) vaccine in rock bream *Oplegnathus fasciatus* at a low rearing temperature. *Vaccine* 32:363–368.
- Pallister J, Goldie S, Coupar B, Shiell B, Michalski WP, Siddon N, Hyatt A. 2007. Bohle iridovirus as a vector for heterologous gene expression. *J Virol Methods* 146:419–423.
- Peiffer LB, Sander S, Gabrielson K, Pessier AP, Allender MC, Waltzek T, Subramaniam K, Stilwell NK, Adamovicz L, Bronson E, Mangus LM. 2019. Fatal ranavirus infection in a group of zoo-housed meller's chameleons (*Trioceos melleri*). *J Zoo Wildl Med* 50:696.
- Picco AM, Brunner JL, Collins JP. 2007. Susceptibility of the endangered California tiger salamander, *Ambystoma californiense*, to Ranavirus infection. *J Wildl Dis* 43:286—290.
- Plumb JA, Grizzle JM, Young HE, Noyes AD, Lamprecht S. 1996. An iridovirus isolated from wild largemouth bass. *J Aquat Anim Health* 8:265–270.
- Plumb JA, Zilberg D. 1999. Survival of largemouth bass iridovirus in frozen fish. *J Aquat Anim Health* 11:94–96.
- Pozet F, Morand M, Moussa A, Torhy C, de Kinkelin P. 1992. Isolation and preliminary characterization of a pathogenic icosahedral deoxyribovirus from the catfish *Ictalurus melas*. *Dis Aquat Organ* 14:35–42.
- Prasankok P, Chutmongkonkul M, Kanchankhan S. 2005. Characterization of iridovirus isolated from diseased marbled sleepy goby, *Oxyeleotris marmoratus*. In Walker PJ, Lester RG, Bondad-Reantaso M (eds) *Diseases in Asian Aquaculture V*. Asian Fisheries Society, Manila.
- Price SJ, Ariel E, Maclaine A, Rosa GM, Gray MJ, Brunner JL, Garner TWJ. 2017. From fish to frogs and beyond: impact and host range of Emergent ranaviruses. *Virology* 511:272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2017.08.001>.
- Price, SJ, Garner TWJ, Nichols RA, Balloux F, Ayres C, Mora-Cabello de Alba A, Bosch J. 2014. Collapse of amphibian communities due to an introduced Ranavirus. *Curr Biol* 24:2586—2591.
- Qin QW, Chang SF, Ngoh-lim GH, Gibson-Kueh S, Shi CY, Lam TJ. 2003. Characterization of a novel ranavirus isolated from grouper *Epinephelus tauvina*. *Dis Aquat Organ* 53:1–9.

- Reddacliff LA, Whittington RJ. 1996. Pathology of epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus (EHNV) infection in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and redbfin perch (*Perca fluviatilis*). *J Comp Pathol* 115:103–115.
- Ridenhour BJ, Storfer AT. 2008. Geographically variable selection in *Ambystoma tigrinum* virus (Iridoviridae) throughout the western USA. *J Evol Biol* 21:1151—1159.
- Robert J, George E, De Jesús Andino F, Chen G. 2011. Waterborne infectivity of the Ranavirus frog virus 3 in *Xenopus laevis*. *Virology* 417:410–417.
- Souza MJ, Gray MJ, Colclough P, Miller DL. 2012. Prevalence of infection by *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* and ranavirus in Eastern Hellbenders (*cryptobranchus alleganiensis alleganiensis*) in eastern Tennessee. *J Wildl Dis* 48:560–566. <https://doi.org/10.7589/0090-3558-48.3.560>.
- Stilwell NK. 2017. Ranaviruses in aquaculture: genetic diversity, improved molecular tools, and experimental analysis of husbandry factors influencing morbidity. PhD dissertation, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL.
- Stilwell NK, Whittington RJ, Hick PM, Becker JA, Ariel E, van Beurden S, Vendramin N, Oleson NJ, Waltzek TB. 2018. Partial validation of a TaqMan real-time quantitative PCR for the detection of ranaviruses. *Dis Aquat Organ* 128:105-116.
- Stöhr AC, López-Bueno A, Blahak S, Caeiro MF, Rosa GM, Alves de Matos AP, Martel A, Alejo A, Marschang RE. 2015. Phylogeny and differentiation of reptilian and amphibian ranaviruses detected in Europe. *PLoS One* doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0118633.
- Svec D, Tichopad A, Novosadova V, Pfaffl MW, Kubista M. 2015. How good is a PCR efficiency estimate: recommendations for precise and robust qPCR efficiency assessments. *Biomol Detect Quantif* 3:9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bdq.2015.01.005>.
- Tan WGH, Barkman TJ, Chinchar VG, Essani K. 2004. Comparative genomic analyses of frog virus 3, type species of the genus ranavirus (family Iridoviridae). *Virology* 323:70–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2004.02.019>.
- Vilaça ST, Bienentreu JF, Brunetti CR, Lesbarrères D, Murray DL, Kyle CJ. 2019. Frog virus 3 genomes reveal prevalent recombination between ranavirus lineages and their origins in Canada. *J Vir* 93(20). <https://doi.org/10.1128/jvi.00765-19>.
- Waltzek TB, Miller DL, Gray MJ, Drecktrah B, Briggler JT, MacConnell B, Hudson K, Hopper L, Friary J, Yun SC, Malm KV, Weber ES, Hedrick RP. 2014. New disease records for hatchery reared sturgeon. I. Expansion of the host range of frog virus 3 into hatchery-reared pallid sturgeon *Scaphirhynchus albus*. *Dis Aquat Organ* 111:219–227.
- Wang F, Flanagan J, Su N, Wang LC, Bui S, Nielson A, Wu X, Vo HT, Ma XJ, Luo Y. 2012. RNAscope: a novel in situ RNA analysis platform for formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissues. *J Mol Diagn* 14:22-9.

- Whitfield SM, Geerdes E, Chacon I, Rodriguez EB, Jimenez RR, Donnelly MA, Kerby JL. 2013. Infection and co-infection by the amphibian chytrid fungus and ranavirus in wild Costa Rican frogs. *Dis Aquat Organ* 104:173–178.
- Whittington RJ, Becker JA, Dennis MM. 2010. Iridovirus infections in finfish—critical review with emphasis on ranaviruses. *J Fish Dis* 33:95–122.
- Whittington RJ, Reddacliff GL. 1995. Influence of environmental temperature on experimental infection of redbfin perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) with epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus, an Australian iridovirus. *Aust Vet J* 72:421–424.
- Woodland JE, Noyes AD, Grizzle JM. 2002. A survey to detect largemouth bass virus among fish from hatcheries in the southeastern USA. *Trans Am Fish Soc* 131:308–311.
- Xu K, Zhu D, Wei Y, Schloegel LM, Chen X, Wang X. 2010. Broad distribution of ranavirus in free-ranging *Rana dybowskii*, in Heilongjiang, China. *Ecohealth* 7:18–23.
- Zhang M, Hu YH, Ziao ZZ, Sun Y, Sun L. 2012. Construction and analysis of experimental DNA vaccines against megalocytivirus. *Fish Shellfish Immunol* 33:1192–1198.
- Zhang D, Iyer LM, Aravind L. 2011. A novel immunity system for bacterial nucleic acid degrading toxins and its recruitment in various eukaryotic and DNA viral systems. *Nucleic Acids Res* 39:4532–4552. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr036>.
- Zilberg D, Grizzle JM, Plumb JA. 2000. Preliminary description of lesions in juvenile largemouth bass injected with largemouth bass virus. *Dis Aquat Organ* 39:143–146.

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Cody earned a B.A. in Spanish and biology from the University of Florida. While completing coursework for his undergraduate degree, he spent time at the Florida Museum of Natural History, sorting and identifying fossils from sediment matrix. He also served as a resident assistant and performed research for the Florida State University Coastal and Marine Lab to better understand shark behavior. Prior to his research on this project, Cody produced an abstract and presented on a study of a novel shark pathogen.